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Research Article

PATTERN OF HOMICIDAL DEATHS AND EFFECTS OF BAN ON LOCAL MANUFACTURING OF FIREARMS

¹Dr Shehroz Sultan, ²Dr Zeeshan Ali, ³Dr Gohar Fraz, ⁴Dr. Muhammad Hasaan Shahid

¹Medical Officer RHC Bhabra Kotmomin, Sargodha, ²Medical Officer Bashir Hospital Sialkot,

³Medical Officer RHC Midh Ranjha, ⁴Medical Officer, Lahore General Hospital, Lahore

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Abstract:

Background: Manslaughter is the most well-known way of unnatural death and numerous kinds of weapons are utilized including guns.

Objectives: To decide the weaponry design in the desperate deaths and audit of writing for deciding the impacts of the prohibition on gun limitations.

Design: Non-interventional (descriptive) type study.

Place and duration of Study: This investigation was led on 759 post-mortem examinations which were performed at Services Hospital, Lahore (July 2018 to March 2019).

Subjects and Methods: Out of 759 post-mortem examinations, 509 cases were of destructive in nature which was investigated based on appropriate accounts and examination of the bodies.

Results: The investigation uncovered the prevalence of gun fatalities, which were 89.19% of the all-out destructive passing. These passing were progressively normal in-country populace (57%) and among guys (85.65%). For the most part, the exploited people were youngsters in their prime and profitable long periods of life for example between 21-40 years. The majority of the guns passing came about because of high-speed rifled weapons (91.62%). The gun wounds were generally situated on the head, neck and face (49.50%). Murderous passing because of guns was noted in (89.19%) of cases.

Conclusion: Our investigation uncovered high recurrence of guns uses for murderous deaths even after the prohibition on the gun. It is proposed that the unlawful dealing of guns ought to be controlled and usage of the laws with respect to weapons ought to be polished, instead of the new enactment.

Key Words: Manslaughter, Death, Weapons, Guns, Prohibition, Intervention, Post-Mortem, Destructive, Fatalities and Encasement.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Shehroz Sultan**

Medical Officer RHC Bhabra Kotmomin, Sargodha.

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INTRODUCTION:

Instruments (weapons) intentionally intended for a strike, advanced quickly. With the disclosure of explosive, came logically increasingly amazing guns. By definition, weapon is an article made or adjusted for causing real hurt [1]. Injury delivering specialists (weapons) of criminological significance have been characterized from various perspectives. They have been gathered under headings, for example, mechanical power, warm activities, compound specialists, electromagnetic power, asphyxia, and embolic injury. As found in medico legitimate practice, blends of injury often happen, having been brought about by a solitary agent [2]. Injuries are brought about by the use of physical brutality to the body, contingent on how they are caused for example by unpolished power, sharp weapon or guns [3]. Firearms are the central wellspring of causing wounds all through present-day world. Manslaughter is the slaughtering of one individual by another [1]. When one individual executes another, the wrongdoing needs an examination to carry the guilty party to equity. A post-mortem examination is the fundamental examination to set up whether the demise is or not because of common causes. On the off chance that it isn't because of characteristic illness, at that point it must be credited to one of these reasons: mishap, suicide or homicide [2]. There has been a worldwide increment in wrongdoings thus in manslaughter [3]. The explanation behind this is numerous folds and it needs intensive testing into the evolving social, conservative, and social situation. The deadliest type of brutality in the USA is firearm viciousness [7]. From 1987 to 1993, the gun manslaughter rate multiplied for those matured 15-24 in the USA [4]. In 2000, 75685 individuals (27/100000) endured non-lethal gun firearm shot wounds [5]. The simple accessibility of weapons and wide spread display of savagery in media has demonstrated an impression of the equivalent in our nation. The primary driver of crime/unnatural deaths in the public eye are ascribed to money related, social and family debates. Manslaughter is the most widely recognized way of unnatural deaths. The level of maniacal deaths in the year 1999 revealed at Forensic Medicine Department was 82.6%. The guns were utilized in the greatest number of cases 88.0% [10]. Previously, gun weapons were unreservedly accessible, out of which for the most part weapons were privately made. So, Government restricted the nearby assembling of these weapons trusting that example of injuring ought to be changed because of the prohibition on assembling of these famous weapons. So, the investigation of the weaponry designs in murderous deaths was arranged

and audit of writing was led, to decide the impact of the restriction on guns.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

This investigation was led on 759 post-mortem examinations which were performed at Services Hospital, Lahore (July 2018 to March 2019). It watched the appropriation with respect to the sex of people/unfortunate casualties, the environment, age circulation of the perished, and the weaponry designs for such deaths uncovered at dissection examination. All out 759 post-mortem examinations were performed in the funeral home. Out of which 509 cases were of maniacal in nature and were considered in detail. These cases were chosen based on legitimate narratives and examination of the bodies. Significant records of the cases for example medico lawful testaments; bed head tickets, activity notes and Police records were investigated. Examination of garments has been finished. The locales and sizes of the cuts/tears/slug's openings and the appropriation of the blood recolours in connection to basic injuries were noted. Outside examination of the wounds in every one of the locales of the body was led. The wounds were graphed and numbered in every district. The sizes, shapes and precise destinations of the wounds were noted. The inner examination was led and all the viscera and organs in the three principle depressions (cranial, thoracic and stomach cavity) were inspected. The majority of these unfortunate casualties had different gun wounds. The wounds were contemplated and gathered by the weapon utilized, for example, sharp weapon's wounds, obtuse weapon's injury and gun's wounds. The two guys and females of any age who kicked the bucket of the maniacal curse were incorporated. Cases from both provincial and urban environment were incorporated. Dubious cases about the way deaths were avoided. Deaths because of poisonings and dead bodies experiencing rot were prohibited from the investigation. The babies that kicked the bucket in the uterus due to the demise of the mother were likewise barred.

RESULTS:

Out of 509 post-mortems having a murderous history of death, done at Forensic Department, in 454 dissections the reason for death was gun wounds. Both the urban and country police headquarters elude their cases to this division for post-mortem examination. In an absolute number of 509 post-mortem examinations, 292 (57%) post-mortems originated from provincial territories, 146 (29%) dissections were from the urban zone and 71 were eluted from the different locale of the area.

Figure – I: Residence wise distribution of Homicide Victims

Table – I: The age distribution of the deceased (509)

Ages	Number	Percentages
0-10	16	3.14 °A
11-20	44	8.64 °Z0
21-30	184	36.14 °Zo
31-40	134	26.32 °Z0
41-50	57	11.19 °Zo
51-60	37	7.26 °A
61-70	28	5.50 %
70-Above	9	1.76 °A

Hence the gun deaths were more in the rustic zones when contrasted with urban setup. The male subjects (436) 85.65 % commanded the female’s number (73) 14.34 % with a proportion of 6:1 In the age bunch appropriation, for the most part, the unfortunate casualties were youngsters in their prime and profitable long stretches of life. 184 (36.14%) cases were in the age gathering of 21 – 30 years. 134 (26.32%) cases were in the age gathering of the 31-multi-year. The most reduced number of unfortunate casualties were at the outrageous of ages, 16 were in the age gathering of 0 – 10 years and 09 (1.76%) exploited people were in the age gathering of 70-above.

Figure – II: Weaponry Pattern in homicidal deaths

The weaponry example received for murderous deaths uncovered at post-mortem examination that the most astounding number of lethal wounds 454 (89.19%) was because of guns weapons. These weapons incorporate a wide range of guns for example high speed since quite a while ago zoomed, short dashed, rifled and smooth exhausted. The least number of unfortunate casualties 18 (3.5%) was because of obtuse weapons while the rest of the 24 (4.7%) were because of sharp-edged weapons. Some maniacal cases 13 (2.55%) were because of different causes for example Strangulation. The anatomical areas of lethal

wounds were resolved in each of the 509 cases. A large portion of these cases have more than one damage and situated on numerous locales of the body. The general territory of the head including neck and face was the most widely recognized site, which represented 252 (49.5%) wounds. The number of wounds in the chest was 170 (33.39%), which was the following regular region focused on the body. An aggregate of 82 (16.1%) wounds was recorded in the stomach zone amid the examination. Both the upper appendages and lower appendages continued an aggregate of 5 wounds (0.98%).

Table – II: Regional distribution of injuries in homicidal cases

Region involved.	Number	Percentages
Head, Neck, Face	252	49.50%
Thorax	170	33.39%
Abdomen	82	16.11%
Extremities	5	0.98 %
Total	509	100%

DISCUSSION:

The way of death clarifies how the reason for death happened. Murders are one of them. Manslaughters are extremely basic everywhere throughout the world. In an examination at Cape Town, it was seen that the five fundamental savagery and damage mortality classes were murders 46%, transport mishaps 29%, fire 8%, suicide 7% and suffocating 2% of all non-characteristic mortality [7]. In another investigation in USA crime stays one of the main sources of death for youngsters [8]. At Loss Angles manslaughters were the main source of awful deaths 45.3% pursued by mishaps 31%. The general murder rate per 100,000 populace was 14.0 [9]. In our examination, there were 509 post-mortem examinations, which were because of destructive deaths. Out of which 292 cases (57%) were from country territories, 146 cases (29%) were from urban regions and 71 cases (14%). These outcomes are about the same to a past report in Bahawalpur in which country contribution in murders was increasingly (58.1%) at that point urban populaces (42%) [10]. These outcomes can likewise be contrasted with crafted by different agents on the planet. In an investigation, it was seen that as provincial zones have a higher level of brutal deaths than urban areas [11]. In another examination, it was seen that more deaths (from discharge wounds) happened in the rustic territories than the cities [12]. The aftereffects of these worldwide investigations are the same as our discoveries. This sort of provincial and urban natural surroundings demonstrates the all-inclusive community dispersion in our nation, which

is of country strength. In everywhere throughout the world guys are more associated with crimes than females. In an examination on age-related examples of vicious deaths, it was seen that guy out numbered females in homicides [13]. In another investigation, it was seen that there were 329 injury related deaths in Diyarbakir in 1997 in which 226 were male (69%) and 103 were females (31%) [14]. In an investigation, 83 crimes (by guns) were enlisted in 10 years in which 58% unfortunate casualties were guys and 42% exploited people were females [15]. Our examination additionally demonstrated a similar factor of male dominance, which was 85.65% around there. The female exploited people were just 14.34%. These outcomes are the same as in a past report in Pakistan in which the male exploited people were 87% and the female unfortunate casualties were just 13% [10]. In the event that we think about these examinations it winds up obvious this is a result of the actualities our general public is male overwhelming and females are typically bound to their homes. Our examination demonstrated the most extreme maniacal deaths in the age gathering of 21-30 years. The periods of the unfortunate casualties around there were actually equivalent to in a past report, in which the age bunch for the most part engaged with crimes was 21-30 years [10]. Our outcomes about the age association here were nearly equivalent to in different examinations [10]. In our investigation methods of reasoning for this observing is by all accounts the ensured gathering of 0-10 years and 50-above in our general public, as the children and elders are minded more and henceforth

making them less helpless against damage. Our examination likewise uncovered that weapons included were generally the guns 454 (89.19%) all things considered and the second strategy embraced for the desperate reason for existing was the utilization of sharp-edged weapons 4.71% here. The investigation at Newfoundland in which sharp-edged weapons were the most widely recognized technique and the investigation of Costa Rica in which cutting/penetrating were progressively basic strategies utilized for killings negate our outcomes [16, 17]. This is a result of the way that in Newfoundland and Costa Rica guns are not uninhibitedly accessible. While our examination compares with the past investigation in which guns were the most generally utilized weapons for manslaughters. In another investigation at the USA, it was assessed that the emotional increment in the US crime rate from 1985-93 was because of an enduring increment in guns murders [18, 19]. Guns were utilized in almost 70% of all crimes in the USA. The continuous utilization of guns in these investigations just as in our examination is a result of the way that guns are unreservedly accessible to the general population of these zones. The overall pirating of guns and disappointment of enactments in such manner is assuming a noteworthy job.

Wounds were recorded in every one of the cases and audit of these wounds demonstrated that greatest quantities of 252 wounds were exacted on the zone of Head, Neck and Face. It is because of the basic conviction that the most significant indispensable organs of the body on which life depends are stopped in the regions of head, neck and face. The chest had 170 wounds, the second most usually affected locale of the body. The stomach area of the body uncovered 82 wounds in this investigation, in which at least one significant viscera was harmed prompting demise. Maniacal shooting made a couple of gun wounds the limits and in this examination, the upper and lower appendages demonstrate just 5 lethal wounds in 509 exploited people. In a comparative report at Oslo and Copenhagen in which crime by gun was talked about, it was discovered that most exploited people were shot in the head. In another examination at Texas, it was expressed that guns wounds to the head are frequently lethal and routinely experienced in the act of Forensic Pathology in the USA [20, 21]. On the in spite of our outcomes there was an examination in Eastern Saudi Arabia on gun fatalities, in which it was discovered that most exploited people were shot in the chest (41%) and after that head (34%) [22]. Same were the outcomes in an investigation at Sweden on murderous and self-destructive sharp power fatalities in which most injuries were found in chest and guts in casualties

of crime [23]. Be that as it may, as in our investigation the guns were the most widely recognized weapons utilized for manslaughters so the head and neck was the perfect site for curse prompting quick and beyond any doubt passing. Crime was the most widely recognized way (82.6%) of unnatural deaths in the year 1999 and the guns were utilized in the greater part number of cases (88.0%) [6]. Weapons were unreservedly accessible in the past due to their neighborhood producing in inborn regions. From that point forward, this nearby assembling was prohibited by the Government so the example of injuring ought to be changed and the rate of manslaughter because of guns ought to be dropped down after the boycott. Our investigation of late weaponry design in desperate deaths uncovered that there is no adjustment in the event of murderous deaths because of guns after the enactment on arms, as a contrast with past study in 1999 [6]. Instead of our outcomes, in an investigation at Colombia in which the impact of prohibition on conveying guns on murders was considered [23]. It was presumed that the occurrence of crimes was lower amid periods when the guns conveying boycott was as a result of contrasted and different periods. Not at all like the individuals who supporter weapon control, culprits comprehend that forbidding guns helps crooks. Runners and secret machine shops supply the black market with everything from hand firearms to completely programmed weapons [24, 25].

CONCLUSION:

Our examination uncovered high recurrence of gun wounds amid dissection. Past looking to control the deadly weapons utilized in viciousness, clinicians have concentrated intercessions on the course reason for savage conduct. These intercessions incorporate numerous exercises as of now inside the domain of wellbeing experts, including screening, quiet training, treatment and support. The instruction of the general population ought to be improved about weapons. The unlawful dealing of guns ought to be controlled and diminished. Execution of the laws in regards to weapons ought to be by and by as opposed to the new enactment.

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